

Budapest University of Technology and Economics
Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Informatics
Department of Telecommunications and Media Informatics

Implementing cloud control for industrial robots using 5G

MASTER'S THESIS

Author
Marcell Balogh

Advisor
Dr. Attila Vidács

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Kivonat

A gyárakban használt ipari robotok többsége előre beprogramozott cselekvéssorozatot hajt végre. Az Ipar 4.0 koncepcióban azonban a gyártás sokkal rugalmasabban konfigurálhatóvá válik majd. Ehhez hozzátevé az 5G vezeték nélküli rádiós és hálózati kommunikációs technológia képességeit, egészen újszerű, intelligens és agilis robotrendszerek megvalósítása válik lehetővé. A kulcs a hálózati erőforrások és a vezeték nélküli hozzáférés rugalmasságának kiaknázásában rejlik.

Diplomamunkám során ROS robot operációs rendszer segítségével megvalósítok egy olyan generikus megoldást, amelyben egy ipari robot eszközre illesztett 3D kamerával lehetővé válik a környezeti információk feldolgozása. Létrehozok egy minta alkalmazást az egyetemen elérhető 5G pilot hálózaton a rendelkezésre álló robotok segítségével úgy, hogy mind a robotvezérlés, mind pedig a kamera képfeldolgozó funkciói is a felhőben találhatóak. A valós környezet mellett az egész rendszer digitális rendszerét is implementálom, amivel így az esetlegesen fizikailag nem elérhető eszközöket és funkciókat ki tudom váltani. Végezetül szimuláció és mérések segítségével kiértékelem a megvalósított rendszer teljesítményét.

Abstract

Most of the industrial robots used in modern factories are performing simple pre-programmed tasks with very limited intelligence. In the concept of Industry 4.0, production becomes more flexible and configurable, enhancing industrial automation. By combining these systems with the potential of 5G network, a whole new intelligent and agile realization of robotic system become available. The key emphasis is on exploiting network resources and flexible wireless connections.

In my thesis I propose a generic solution where I equip industrial robots with 3D camera to be able to perceive information about the environment. I create a demonstration setup using the university's 5G pilot network where both the robot control and the image processing units of the available robotic devices are realized in the cloud. Besides the physical realization I create a digital twin simulation from the real system in Gazebo thus I can reproduce the actual unavailable devices in simulated environment. Finally, with measurements and simulations I validate the capability of the realized system.

Chapter 1

Introduction

In the past few years, collaborative robotic systems gained a lot of popularity not only among industrial participants but also among researchers. In the era of strongly spreading 5G networks, the high-bandwidth and low latency performance made remote controlled robotics available. We expect from these systems that robots will be able to adapt to the actual workplace even when they are not hardcoded for a particular task.

Mobile robots can be equipped with a wide range of sensors like laser scanners, ultrasonic sensors or RGBD camera devices. Cameras are powerful sensors in a control loop, because they can predict collisions and guarantee a more accurate positioning. With the Industry 4.0 the utilization of mobile robots used for localisation and mapping are currently very active research area.

To manage various robotic instruments over the network, a cloud robotics framework could help. The goal of these systems is to provide functionality for hardware abstraction and communication between processes over multiple machines, testing tools, visualization and more. It provides a common framework for handling and controlling various devices over the network.

1.1 Motivation

Throughout my academic experience, I worked mostly with cameras – monocular as well as stereo – either mounted on a robotic arm or onto an autonomous mobile robot. In Bachelor's thesis I investigated the capabilities of a collaborative industrial robotic arm, and extended it with a stereo camera. As for demonstration purposes, I implemented a network-controlled real-time precise control logic using visual servoing to be able to move plastic figures by the rules of chess. I also gained

knowledge about developing autonomous mobile robot control from a cloud-based environment.

These experiences led me to combine these fields and examine their network communication over an 5G pilot network. Integrating visual guidance to robots allows me to exploit the potential of ultra-low latency networks and cloud robotic frameworks. With these devices the network parameters could be measured and compared with existing technologies to show performance differences and provide better solutions.

1.2 Task definition

Throughout this thesis work, I introduce the Robot Operating System (ROS) environment with the related Gazebo simulator. I present the hardware elements I worked with, like the Intel RealSense camera, a custom built autonomous mobile robot, and a collaborative robotic arm from Universal Robots.

I implement a generic solution where a 3D camera is integrated to an industrial robot and also to a mobile robot. In order to demonstrate the capabilities of the mentioned devices, I design and realize a common task which is also implemented parallel with digital twins in simulated environment.

The examination of camera streaming consists of comparing the ROS realization and presenting an alternate solution for a faster and cost-effective real time streaming. Each method is implemented separately on the robots to be able to forward images to the cloud for further processing. As a result, image stream from both method is being processed to provide depth image or point cloud for further tasks.

In the end, I show how my solutions improved the network transmission parameters. I also provide insight about how I built up the demonstration scenarios in reality as well as in simulated environment, and show how I integrated the camera to help robots examine their surroundings.

1.3 Outline

This thesis is structured in the following way. In Chapter 2, the background of the applied technologies is introduced alongside with the used hardware devices. The tools of simulated environment and digital twin adaptation is exposed and robotic navigation methods are exposed. The next chapter includes an introduction of my idea of system architecture. It presents the design concept for robotic arms, mobile

robots and the common camera integration. In Chapter 4 the implementation steps are specified. Starting with the mobile robot realization and simulation followed by the robotic arms, all methods are explained here. Chapter 5 and Chapter 6 describes the use cases that are implemented for demonstration purposes. It contains the general experiences and the measurement results are also detailed here. In Chapter 7, the overall result and performance of the implemented system is summarized. It is followed by presenting the conclusion and considerations regarding further improvements and finally, I summarize my task carried out.

Chapter 2

Technological background

In this section I give an overview about the applied methods, and introduce the hardware components. First, I take a look at current technologies, how cloud-based environment and robotics are combined by both researchers and leading industrial companies, and show the typical use cases.

2.1 Literature review

Industrial robots took a long way to reach their current form and the new era of collaborative robots is currently rising. On the contrary of what people believed with the appearance of industrial robots, workers are still essential elements in the factories thus a stronger human-robot cooperation is started to emerge. Robots are able to cooperate even better with humans, taking their presence into account and proceed with caution.

To help robots look around their environment, visual servoing is a popular solution. Visual servoing is an approved technology which was first proposed in 1996 by Hutchinson et al. [1] and significantly improved by F. Chaumette and S. Hutchinson [2]. Nowadays two popular approaches were formalized: Position Based Visual Servoing (PBVS) and Image Based Visual Servoing (IBVS). PBVS seeks to calculate and minimize errors in the global reference frame while IBVS minimize errors in the image plane of the camera.

Autonomous navigation is a prevailing topic among robotic researchers. To tackle with challenges, Kalman Filter is a leading method for sensor fusion [3]. Nguyen et al. proposed a solution for autonomous navigation also with Robot Operating System and Gazebo [4]. They used deep learning with simulation data to improve

real-world application. Authors in [5] proposed an improved algorithm with Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) to estimate the state of a UAV in real time.

To be able to select the most optimal streaming codec, a comparison was carried out in [6]. After thoroughly comparing H.264 Advanced Video Codec, Dirac, Theora and Motion JPEG2000, it clearly indicates the advantage of interframe comparison in H.264.

Visual aided robots require a well-considered approach for a proper real time stream forwarding. Video streaming over cellular or wireless networks is also appears in various fields. A popular and versatile tool for stream forwarding is to utilize GStreamer. A typical use-case of GStreamer is real-time video streaming [7] but it is also useful for acoustic signal processing [8] or even at detecting gravitational waves [9].

2.2 Industry 4.0

There is a new wave of industrial revolution and innovation marked by intelligence. The core of the change is the application of next generation infocommunication technologies. Compared with the traditional manufacturing industry, the future of industry is represented by smart factories where an ideal production system could intelligently judge product attributes, production costs, safety, reliability and sustainability to optimize product customization for each customer [10].

The new way of development in manufacturing industry needs to convert the challenge of flexible production into an opportunity. It needs to use automation technology to solve the problem of flexible production by integrating with the rapid improvement of Internet, IoTs, and other information technologies [11].

2.3 Cloud architecture

Cloud robotics aim at transferring the complexity of computing process into the cloud platform through the latest network technology. This approach significantly reduces the computational load on individual robots and transmit the tasks to high efficiency cloud servers [12]. In cloud robotics, robot cells enjoy compelling advantages like the accessibility of powerful computing units as well as the shared knowledge.

The general architecture consists of two main parts: the cloud platform with its required equipment and the robot hardware with various sensors. The basic idea of

Figure 2.1. Cloud robotics architecture example

cloud robotics is to separate the actuator module from the controller and place it in the cloud. With a reliable and low latency network system, remote controlling is also possible even from great distances. When an actuator is connected to a network, there is no need for on-board computers that calculate movement commands and trajectories. Instead, the controller could run in a cloud environment or as an edge cloud node while the actuator only receives and executes commands coming from the cloud. Due to this improvement, cloud robotic applications cover a wide spectrum of applications and services in different domains including health care, environment monitoring, transportation or entertainment [13].

2.3.1 5G network

For communication in industrial environment there are several well defined Ethernet systems – such as PROFINET, EtherCAT – designed for real-time control of robotic equipment. Although it can fulfil the production requirements, it has drawbacks like the complicated physical cabling among machines which could go through hazardous

areas, increasing the risk of failure. 5G is aimed to replace wired local-area networks with private network cells [14].

The fifth generation cellular mobile networks are expected to support mission critical, ultra-reliable low latency communication (URLLC) services and enhanced broadband applications. 5G network opens the door to cyber-physical systems and Industry 4.0. More devices are connected that are no longer limited to industrial application. With this sharp increase, there is a need for stable and reliable network system that could handle real-time communication among devices and cloud infrastructure. 5G not only enriches user experience, but also provides technical support for artificial intelligence-based applications, such as industry automation, smart healthcare and intelligent transportation systems. As a result, 5G is regarded as the infrastructure of industrial internet and artificial intelligence [15].

More and more companies rapidly prepare to adapt a private 5G cellular network because of the undoubtedly benefits of the new generation cellular network. Besides the existing network options such as Ethernet, WiFi or 4G LTE, 5G is expected to become an even better connectivity solution. Armed with these capabilities, industrial robots can be precisely controlled dynamically with ultra-low latency and be connected to people and machines locally and globally, creating the factory of the future.

2.3.2 ROS1

Robot Operating System (ROS) is an open-source set of libraries and tools aiming to simplify the creation of complex robotic systems [16]. It has a flexible approach to modular robotic architecture and provides APIs for many popular programming languages with proper support of transitions. The main communication scheme follows the popular publish-subscribe and request response pattern which are implemented to be handled by a master that controls all the internal and external communication.

There is a dedicated simulation tool for ROS called Gazebo, where all these complex systems can be modelled. Nowadays leading companies realized the strength of the open-source community and they also started to contribute and provide proper ROS APIs for most of their robotic devices and accessories. This led ROS to be the de facto standard of distributed robotic application development toolkit.

2.3.3 ROS2

Robot Operating System 2 is worth taking into consideration because of its new features and distributed design schemes. ROS2 also offers a wide variety of Quality of Service (QoS) policies that allows to tune communication between nodes. Instead of using a custom transport layer implementation like the UDPROS or TCPROS as in ROS1, ROS2 offers an existing middleware solution, namely the Data Distribution System (DDS). Meanwhile ROS1 is targeting Python2, ROS2 leaves behind Python2 and provides functionality over Python3.6. It also uses C++11, C++14 extensively and C++17 is also on the roadmap for future releases [17].

Figure 2.2. Architectural differences between ROS1 and ROS2

ROS1 does not satisfy real-time run requirements and only runs on a few operating systems. There are no QoS features defined, and it does not guarantee fault-tolerance or process synchronization. On the contrary to these deficiencies of ROS1, ROS2 is created to satisfy the needs of the broader community and new use-cases are considered such as real-time systems, small embedded platforms (like sensor nodes), non-ideal networks and cross-platform compatibility [18]. For further development ROS2 could serve as a basis of modern cloud robotic systems.

There is also a new simulator introduced as Ignition Gazebo [19], to replace the existing solution. Among many new features, the most important update is the option for distributed simulation across several machines.

2.4 Robotic hardware

Robots are traditionally designed and planned to be utilized in industrial environment to do repetitive and limited tasks. With rapid improvement, robots became collaborative and accessible for smaller factories and research facilities. Industrial robotic applications started to examine the possibility of handling robots as coworkers, sharing workspace and tracks with human workers [20].

Robotic arms used in factories are usually consists of joints with multiple degrees of freedom and an end effector to grip elements in pick and place tasks. On the other hand, mobile robots are more complex and versatile devices. Meanwhile robotic manipulators usually perform tasks blindly pre-programmed, mobile robots typically could not operate without sensing their environment.

2.4.1 Industrial mobile robots

Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV) systems were developed into the key component of organized modern intralogistics since the 1950s. AGVs were initially used by the automotive industry in America. With the rapid development of sensory and regulatory technology and microelectronics paved the way for AGVs [21].

The main roles of AGVs are repetitive commissioning while moving objects from A to B. They lack of on-board intelligence and obey simple programming instructions. In the past few years, a new kind of internal logistic system is started to take over from AGVs to Autonomous Mobile Robots (AMRs).

An AMR is equipped with a large variety of sensors and a powerful on board computer to help understand its operating environment. Unlike the AGV-s which are limited to fixed route following along embedded wires or magnets, AMRs can adapt to environmental changes with processing sensor information real-time. They can safely perform the given task even in busy environment.

2.4.2 Collaborative robotic arm

Robot arms belong to the family of manipulators, that are traditionally designed for stationary, monotonous industrial working. The flexible movement is generally allowed by different series of joints, that determine its degrees of freedom (DOF).

The main goal of collaborative robots is to replace human operators in dirty, dangerous, and dull jobs and reduce repetitive strain and accidental injuries. Early robots operated only with a safety cage where a person cannot enter in order to prevent

serious injuries. Nowadays this risk is minimized, robots are prepared to care about their environment, and stop immediately in case of any collision.

Robots have to face with only partially observable environment. They have to work with a huge complex world. Because of the high rate of uncertainty robots have to be prepared for unforeseeable circumstances. To get informed about the environment, it can be equipped with different kind of sensors [22].

2.5 Common sensing elements

Robots can be equipped with a wide range of sensors to be able to get proper information about their environment. With more sensors, the level of confidence is higher but it always comes with a cost. More sensors produce more data which also require load-bearing and high bandwidth transmission from the sensors to the cloud.

The most frequent types of sensors on a mobile robot are lidar, which scans the environment in a horizontal plane. Some robots are also equipped with ultrasonic sensors for distance measurement in a small distance (i.e. stairs, steep gradients). Depth cameras can extend the field of view and give a 3D representation of the surroundings. With the combination of different sensors, a very reliable and safe mobile robot cloud be built, prepared for working together with other robots and humans also.

2.5.1 Lidar

Lidar stands for Light Detection and Ranging. It is generally a two-dimensional laser scanner which produces a set of planar coordinates. Lasers scan their environment by emitting a laser pulse over a spinning mirror. When an emitted laser pulse hits an object, it is reflected back to the laser receiver. The time difference between emitting and receiving is used to calculate distance with millimetre accuracy.

Despite its higher cost, it provides accurate and quick acquisition of object space surface models. Lidars became an essential part of automotive and mobile robots to help detecting their surroundings thus being able to manoeuvre among different dynamical objects. Lidars could serve as a basis of range detection but utilizing cheaper cameras could substitute them with a well-taught AI network.

2.5.2 Pinhole cameras

Cameras are the most essential tools in computer vision. It helps detect and record the environment real-time. During calculations and simulations, a simple model applied, called the pinhole camera model. In this model, the scene view is formed by projecting 3D points into the image plane using a perspective transformation [23]. Applying a pinhole camera model that projects the 3 dimensional world onto a 2 dimensional image plane, the depth of the image will be lost.

Figure 2.3. Pinhole camera model

One of the most relevant parameters is the focal length (f), which is a calculation of an optical distance from the point where light rays converge to form a sharp image of an object to the sensor at the focal plane in the camera. The focal length is determined when the camera lens is focused at infinity.

$$K = \begin{bmatrix} f_x & 0 & 0 \\ s & f_y & 0 \\ c_x & c_y & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.1)$$

The pinhole camera parameters are represented in a 4 by 3 matrix called the camera matrix. This matrix maps the 3D world scene into the image plane. The calibration algorithm calculates the camera matrix using the extrinsic and intrinsic parameters. The extrinsic parameters represent the location of the camera in the 3D scene. The intrinsic parameters are the focal length (f_x, f_y), the principal point which is also known as optical centre (c_x, c_y), and the skew coefficient (s) which is non-zero if the

image axes are not perpendicular. The intrinsic camera matrix (K) is defined with the mentioned parameters as Equation 2.1 describes.

2.5.3 3D sensing methods

The common attribute of 3D-cameras is that they are able to measure spatial distance based on different options. Typically, stereo-cameras consists of two gray-scale cameras, from disparity is calculated. This could be also done by combining two colour sensing cameras. The other kind of 3D-camera is the RGBD camera which gives the depth and colour information, too. In most cases, it refers to a Kinect-style camera (i.e. RealSense, ZED). Besides providing colour and depth, these could also create monochrome or coloured point cloud.

Most image processing methods operate on colour channels of the images but there are other attributes like depth sensing, which also provides useful information. With the spreading of Kinect sensors, as an ultimate example of depth sensing, this technology become a frequently used extension of RGB cameras.

While most lidars detect object in a horizontal plane, depth cameras have more versatile functionality. Creating point cloud from depth camera stream could cover the surroundings not only in planar but in a wider range of observation. A typical usage is to project point cloud to a 2D plane to be able to handle these data as it would have come from a laser scanner.

2.5.4 Point cloud representation

Point clouds represent 3D objects or shapes with a vast set of spatial coordinates. It can be calculated from depth maps or laser scanners directly. It is a typical product of stereo cameras to help understand their environment. Utilization of point clouds is a very current field of study, there are several ongoing research topics about its application and processing methods.

Working with point clouds usually means a pre-processed set of points instead of the raw dataset. Downsampling is done with a voxel grid filter. A voxel (volume pixel) is equivalent with a pixel extended to three dimensional space, which can be represented as a unit cube. During downsampling the points in space are being bucketed into voxels with a given size. Therefore, each occupied voxel generates one exact point by averaging all points inside.

For example, Figure 2.4 represent these downsampling steps where the increasing size of individual voxels (V_{voxel}) results in decreasing point components. The starting

Figure 2.4. Different levels of point cloud downsampling

point cloud consists of 10 000 points but downsampled with only 0.05 size voxel still show it as a cube filled with points almost half a size as the original cloud. This method often used as a pre-processing step as it drastically reduces the number of points yet still keeps the shape of the spatial objects recognisable.

2.6 Coordinate system transformation

To describe the joint transformations among hardware components, ROS uses Universal Robot Description File (URDF) format. It is defined by an XML format to represent a robot model containing the kinematic and dynamic description, visual representation and the collision model. URDF files consist of a set of link components and a set of joint elements. It is a universal representation for real as well as simulated robots. To help creating shorter and more readable XML files, URDF could contain XML macros called Xacros. It is a useful package to simplify large robot descriptions with named property blocks, math expressions, conditional blocks or rospack commands.

The transform library (TF) can manage the relations among multiple coordinate systems, also called frames, changing over time in a transparent way. In most robotic applications especially robots with multiple degrees of freedom, a well-defined link of transformations – transform tree – is required to follow the changes over time. TF builds a tree like graph of transforms between frames, and can support multiple disconnected trees. It can operate in a distributed system so that all the information about the coordinate frames of a robot is available to all ROS components on any connected device in the network.

Another advantage of transformation links is that it does not distinguish between real and simulated robot. In both cases look the same which significantly improves modular robotic development and testing with digital twin simulation.

2.7 Mobile robot navigation

More and more robots are operating in indoor environment to help increase productivity. However, to do so, it requires a map to retrieve information about the possible routes from A to B. At the first start, the robot has no information about the actual environment, it can only rely on the surroundings available from 3D cameras and lidar sensors. To obtain a persistent map, either needs an uploaded map or it can create its own by discovering its environment with Simultaneous Localization And Mapping (SLAM) methods.

Robot Operating System provides Navigation Stack to help robot navigation [24]. Although the idea is quite simple, the implementation could be challenging in case of multiple different sensors. Navigation Stack assumes that the actual robot communicates with standard ROS messages and it is configured in a particular way described in its documentation [25]. Navigation stack does not require a map to operate but the typical way is to use it for navigating over an existing map.

2.7.1 Map representation

After finishing the mapping process an Occupancy Grid Map (OGM) is created to visualize the real environment in a simple way. Occupancy grid map provides a straightforward representation yet it does not need huge computing capacity. The downside is the lack of accuracy, because if an object falls inside a portion of a grid cell, the whole cell is marked occupied. In an example snippet of OGM in Figure 2.5, the white pixels represent the free cells, the black pixels represent occupied cells and the grey pixels are not yet discovered.

Figure 2.5. Occupancy grid map with a robot model

Map files are stored as images in a supported format, such as PNG, JPEG or PGM. Since maps are represented as image files, it can be easily modified with an editor.

This allows to tidy up any map that created from sensor data, remove things that should not be there, or add fake obstacles subsequently to influence path planning.

2.7.2 Costmap layers

A costmap is a two-dimensional map layer that takes in sensor data from the world - either simulated or real - and builds a 2D or 3D occupancy grid of the data. Then it inflates costs in a 2D costmap based on the occupancy grid map and a user specified inflation parameters [25]. There are two main types: static layer, which contains the walls and other elements that are constant over time, and an obstacle layer with the dynamically changing environment like other AMRs, people, swing doors etc.

Each costmap layer is configured to show a specific sensor information such as there is a separate layer for laserscanner information and another for point cloud from camera. These dynamic costmaps are then layered over each other to form the global map to navigate from.

2.7.3 Trajectory planning

ROS navigation module is divided into a global and local planner where the first one is responsible for finding an optimal path knowing the static elements, and the second one works as a controller by adjusting this path by taking into account the dynamic objects.

Global planner operates over the global costmap to find a minimum cost plan from a start point to an end point in a grid, using generally A* or Dijkstra's algorithm. It generates a series of waypoints for the local planner to follow. Therefore, it is important to take into account the obstacles shown by local costmap. If there is a swing door which is not marked on the global costmap, the global planner will generate a trajectory through the closed door. If the robot gets close to this door, the rolling window of the local planner will prevent the robot going through it.

Local planner is more like a controller rather than a trajectory planner. The goal of a local planner is to take the global plan along with the local costmap and produce command velocity messages that will presumably move the robot towards the goal. It chooses appropriate velocity commands for the robot to traverse the current segment of the global path. The objective is to combine sensory and odometry data with both global and local costmaps. It can alternate the robot's path on the fly in order to keep the robot from striking objects that may endanger its surroundings, yet still allowing it to reach its destination. It implements the trajectory rollout and

Dynamic Window Algorithm (DWA) [26]. The goal of DWA is to produce a (v, w) pair that represents a circular trajectory optimized for the robot's local condition. DWA will only consider velocities within a dynamic window, which is defined to be the set of velocity pairs reachable within the next time interval given the current translational and rotational velocities and accelerations [27].

2.8 Robot arm manipulation

There is an increasing interest in robots which have to work in close proximity to humans in cluttered environment involved with several obstacles and with people moving in and out of the robot workspace. Robot arms have to take care about their surroundings and be aware of the need to avoid any collisions with humans or other obstacles [20].

To influence motion planning, robot joints can be restricted to operate between angles, or spatial objects could be defined as constraints to restrict the robot's freedom partially as well as globally. Robot Operating System contains MoveIt! which is a set of software packages designed specifically for mobile manipulation [27]. It is able to generate collision free motion plans in fairly cluttered workplace with sensors monitoring the environment.

A popular option to equip robot manipulators with sensors is the eye in hand approach, when a camera is rigidly mounted on the end effector of the robot [28]. This can provide partial but precise sight of the robot cell. Other solution is where an external camera observes the robot within its environment called eye to hand. Both approaches have their own advantages and drawbacks that depends on the actual task and workplace.

2.9 Digital twin for robot adaptation

With the increasing computational power of consumer available computers, simulations become widely used before the installation of critical and expensive robotic applications to prevent or predict malfunctions in real world scenarios. For accurate simulation of complex systems, proper physical models needed in order to get the expected outcome. Nowadays simulators are making it possible to rapidly test algorithms, design robots and perform accurate computation including indoor and outdoor environments.

Gazebo is a standalone simulation software that provides ROS wrappers to create interfaces for robot simulation using ROS messages, services and dynamic features. Gazebo's advantage is its support of multiple realistic physics engines such as Open Dynamics Engine (ODE), Simbody or Bullet. It can calculate with the main physical attributes like gravity, friction or wind resistance. It supports ROS robot model description structure called URDF, where one can describe robot elements in XML like syntax, not only the visual parts, but the links, joints and collisions also. This makes possible for leading companies to create the model of their robotics related product to use it in complex projects and simulate sensor behaviour like lidars, cameras and many different devices together.

Chapter 3

System design

In this part I present my system architecture for camera integration. I describe, how the software and hardware connections look like in case of the robot arm and also for the mobile robot. First, I introduce the common architecture, how the common camera element could take place and then I go through the robots one by one. I show the architecture with the main blocks and I also give an insight into the simulated environment.

3.1 Common system architecture

ROS based systems fit well into the concepts of cloud architecture. Sensors are providing real-time information which is being sent over the network, while data is processed in the cloud, and only the acting commands are being sent back to the robot. In this scheme complex sensor networks could easily be managed and processed data off board.

With the spreading of ultra-reliable low latency communication (URLLC) networks, wide bandwidth makes possible to equip robots with more sensors and transmit data near real-time. Cameras are precise and effective sensing elements but they producing large amount of information that needs to be transferred properly to the processing unit.

Large variety of different applications can be realized using the same design patterns that the ROS ecosystem provides. I introduce two use cases where several important features of the above introduced network could be exploited utilizing a collaborative robotic arm and an autonomous mobile robot. The focus is on the modularity of elements especially the integration of the same camera to the different robots in real environment and in simulation also. Although the realized applications could

seem to be slightly different, the underlying communication scheme, network usage and the camera integration follows the similar pattern. The goal is to show the similarities, advantages and drawbacks evidenced by measurement results.

3.2 Mobile robot system architecture

In my AMR system design as Figure 3.1. shows, both the realization and the digital twin model follow the same concept and use common packages. The camera is identical with the device used at the manipulator and also the simulated camera has the same optical parameters. This design allows to mix these setups that could demonstrate a real running mobile robot and a simulated AMR in a common environment.

Figure 3.1. AMR system design

In case of the AMR, the components structured as Figure 3.1 illustrates. Since this AMR is a ROS-free device, it gives the opportunity for implementing custom nodes with a tailor-made communication model. Replacing the ROS image transport with

a custom solution provides more flexibility and significantly reduced bandwidth requirement

There is a local node on the AMR that forwards encoded depth stream for cloud processing. In the cloud, a converter node takes place that transforms this stream, and converts it to ROS messages to be able to integrate back into ROS environment. This ROS compatible depth message is then being transformed to point cloud, which could be integrated into the navigation stack.

3.3 Mobile robot simulation environment

From time to time, unforeseen situations could occur with blocking the ability of development on physical devices, therefore a digital twin simulation could provide a solution. To be prepared for, I built a simulation environment in Gazebo as a digital twin representation. It offers an advantageous area for testing and modelling the navigation stack and different kind of sensor behaviours.

A simulator could easily handle a huge number of instantiated AMRs and present their common navigation skills. Unfortunately, Gazebo could not offer distributed simulation over the network. This means everything is calculated where the simulation is started which is quite inefficient for scalability. Therefore, simulation could not represent the network delays, because everything runs in local machines.

Figure 3.2. Simulated environment for AMR

Figure 3.2 shows my minimal test track design for navigation and sensor testing. My goal is to prepare an environment where the advantage of mounting a 3D camera is clearly visible. To present this, I created a challenging map which shows two different routes with various obstacles. There is a roadblock where the AMR could not go through and a tunnel like table, where the robot could pass. This situation meant to be solved with sensor fusion and navigation.

3.4 Robot arm system architecture

The robotic manipulator architecture follows the principles of cloud robotics via ROS. Instead of using the graphical programming interface that the pendant provides, the robot is fully controlled over the network. The RealSense depth camera is connected to a Raspberry device which functions as a ROS node with providing the camera topics. The camera itself is mounted onto the end effector to be in the end of the robot arm frame and be able to see the grasped objects also.

Figure 3.3. Collaborative robot arm system design

In this setup, the robot controllers could be moved to the edge-cloud along with the computing-intensive tasks such as image processing. To provide images for object detection, a Raspberry Pi functions as a camera driver ROS node to serve images to the image processing services. Image processing consists of working with colour and depth images. From colour image, the elements are segmented, and their pose is calculated to grip it with the robot. The depth image is used for measurement

tasks. The robot has to know, where to put the next element, where an accurate z-distance is a key element.

The UR3e control box also has a Raspberry Pi connected, where the robot controller could run from. Instead of using the teach pendant, the arm could be controlled externally over 5G. Due to its ultra-low latency requirements, it is not yet possible to move UR3e controller node to the cloud and run it over the pilot network, but future improvements will make it possible.

3.5 Robot arm simulation environment

The principal goal of creating a simulation model is to be able to influence the trajectory planning, and test the abilities of object detection and recognition. This simulation is also created in Gazebo, and inspected from the robot visualization tool called rviz. To prepare a simulation environment, Universal Robots provide a good start with official examples supporting ROS1 and ROS2 also. The available codebase contains the robot driver and the robot model files.

Figure 3.4. Real and simulated environment for the robot arm

In this case the original UR3e robot model file is extended with an OnRobot gripper model and a custom-made camera carrier for the RealSense depth camera. This setup on Figure 3.4. shows, how it can build a tower from jenga bricks with respect to its environment. It knows from where can access to jenga elements, and where to put them. There is no hardcoded position, the robot inspects the environment with the camera, measure the distance and decide where to put the next element. It also gets feedback from the gripper fingertip sensors whether it is holding an object or not.

3.6 Camera integration

Camera can be found on the AMR and also on the robot arm. It helps navigating in their environment with respect to the surroundings. The common part of the integration is the resulting transformation tree and the available topics. Transform tree tracks the relationship between coordinate frames in the following graph structure. In most cases it is connected to the robot base link which serves as a virtual basis of the actual device.

Figure 3.5. Camera transformation tree visualization

This structure in Figure 3.5 is defined in the provided URDF file of the camera. To connect the camera, these links need to be included in the actual URDF file of the robot. It does not matter whether the sensor information comes from the simulation or the real one, these links need to be defined correctly. In case of a simulated camera, an additional Gazebo plugin is also required to provide image from the inside of the simulated world model. Custom equipped cameras have to be aligned precisely in the simulation with respect to the real-world location.

In some cases, robots could operate with multiple cameras. To achieve this, camera URDF file have to be ready for arranging the components into a common namespace and handle multiple devices in the same environment. In order to illustrate the usage of namespaces, the following example is given:

```
/amr1/front/camera/depth/image_raw
```

- *amr*: prefix with the robot type and a unique ID. Devices with ID 0 refers to the physical device, above means the simulated AMRs
- *front*: location, where the camera is positioned on the device

- *camera*: the actual node name and the specifics

This example topic provides depth image in raw format from the amr1 device. It could mean real and simulated camera, but conventionally the zero belongs to the real device and all the other is the simulated ones. This transparent naming makes possible to easily switch between simulation and reality because the message structure did not differ.

Chapter 4

Implementation

This chapter introduces how the previously introduced architectural elements were realized. I explain how a modular camera element could be placed onto different robotic hardwares including the simulation. I show the advantages and drawbacks of the current development stack and how I overcome the problems I had to face. Starting with the camera related development I go through the use-case related image processing methods in real application and simulation also, and the several corresponding tasks that needed to be solved.

4.1 Time synchronization

Time synchronization is an essential and critical element of the whole system from every aspect. Without using the exact same time, robots would share outdated information about their environment which could lead to non continuous movements and hazardous situations. In extreme cases it could also trigger an emergency stop, from where robots cannot recover autonomously and require external intervention.

In order to prevent the Real Time Clock (RTC) of robots slowly drifting away from each other at varying degrees I chose Chrony [29] as a network time server, which is a versatile implementation of the Network Time Protocol (NTP). I synchronized the robot clients connected to a Docker container running Chrony to provide a reference time from the cloud server. I configured Chrony so that it could use the real time clock from the host system.

To increase security, Chrony supports Network Time Security (NTS) which is a new authentication scheme for NTP. It enables clients to check and verify packets whether it has been modified in transit. With this improvement, attackers could only delay or drop packets but cannot modify.

Because of the mobile robot is a custom-built vehicle, it provides full access to both hardware and software components. This allows a neat time synchronization setup. I installed Chrony as an NTP client, and configured it to connect to the Chrony cloud server. After testing the connection, the AMR real time clock is synchronized to the cloud.

4.2 Camera module

Camera module is designed to be a universal component that provide real-time stream from the RealSense device through the network reaching the image processing nodes in the cloud. It could be followed by application specific processing nodes that provide the required data.

In general, I realized such camera package that capable of forwarding near real-time stream in both real and simulated environment. Using camera in simulation requires more integration task in order to be properly connected to the simulated robot and provide the related topics. I show, how I processed these images further for demonstration use-cases.

4.2.1 Image forwarding

To the Intel D435i camera, Intel provides a RealSense SDK 2.0 [30]. It is an extensive development kit supporting ROS, OpenCV, Point Cloud Library (PCL) etc. In my case, the ROS wrapper was not an option since it is meant to be a ROS-free device. I have to take into account that the NUC has a limited computing capacity and it runs on accumulators. I also have to integrate into the cloud architecture, so my goal was to provide a lightweight transport node with minimal pre-processing task to forward camera stream from the mobile robot to the cloud server for further processing.

After looking for a lightweight solution, I chose GStreamer to work with. GStreamer is a current open-source multi-platform multimedia framework with widespread API options like the OpenCV library, OpenGL, RealSense or other community-driven projects [31]. It became popular for streaming audiovisual content and has been frequently used in studies relating to video transmission for its utility and flexibility in the delivery of audio and visual content. The multimedia pipelines of GStreamer are completed through the use of plugins which are assembled using so called pads to form an interconnected framework, moving video from the sink pad of a plugin to act as the source of another.

In my case, the common part in ROS and ROS-free image transport is the OpenCV Library. To exploit its capabilities, I compiled on both sender and receiver side with GStreamer integration. After that I could construct the pipeline. The goal of Gstreamer in this project is to separate the application (e.g. video player, video editor) from the streaming media complexity (e.g. hardware acceleration, remoteness). The speciality of my case is that I do not have to bother about the audio track, only the video transmission counts.

Figure 4.1. Sender pipeline

Having regard to the restrictions and specialities of my use case, I set up the pipeline as Figure 4.1 shows. Because of my pipeline forwards pre processed images from OpenCV, I insert these data into the GStreamer pipeline directly from my script. To encode the live camera stream, I applied H.264 encoding, which is also known as MPEG-4 Advanced Video Codec (AVC). Besides H.264 encoding, MJPEG (Motion JPEG) is also a popular encoder. The main difference is that in MJPEG, each frame is encoded individually as a JPEG and it only compresses individual frames of video (each frame as JPEG) whereas H.264 compress across frames. This inter frame compression significantly reduces bandwidth consumption because most frames record only the changes from the previous frame.

In order to be able to send the H.264 stream over the network, it needs to be encapsulated into Real-time Transport Protocol (RTP) [32] packets. After providing the H.264 payload, I combined it with UDP and as a result, it is ready to be sent through the network.

Figure 4.2. Receiver pipeline

In receiver side the pipeline looks as Figure 4.1 presents. In this case, the source is an UDP connection with a related port number. Upon receiving the datagram it is followed by a decoder that extracts H.264 video from RTP packets and sends to another converter which creates a raw formatted stream with the requested parameters (640x480 resolution, 8-bit grayscale) which could be managed by OpenCV. After the stream is handed over to OpenCV, it is ready for ROS integration. With OpenCV, the image stream is then packed into a ROS compliant message type called *sensor_msgs/Image message*. After this conversion, the image stream is being published on a ROS topic.

4.2.2 Depth image conditioning

To get access to the frames from the camera I used Python2 with the RealSense SDK. I created a RealSense pipeline configuration for depth stream with 640x480 resolution and 16-bit depth values, with 30 frames per second (FPS). This provides a detailed raw depth image as Figure 4.3 a) shows, but it still needs to be conditioned for a better quality. To choose the most effective methods, I examined Intel’s depth post processing article [33].

Figure 4.3. Before and after depth image pre-processing

First, I applied an edge-preserving spatial filter, which smooth the depth noise while attempting to preserve edges. In a noisy measurement it will smooth the data but could result in unwanted artifacts such as rounded or elongated edges. Next, I used temporal filtering and hole filling. It is also advised to do whenever possible, making sure not to let holes - where the depth equals zero – influence calculations. It is done by an exponential moving average (EMA) filter which is also used for spatial filtering. With an accurate parameter, I tried to reduce temporal smoothing near

edges and also do not include holes. Figure 4.3 presents the before and after in case of the jenga depth detection. It clearly shows, how the holes were eliminated, and the contours are more accurate. This enhancement is an important step before turning it to a point cloud too.

Although in Figure 4.4 the left image could seem to be less detailed, the transformed point cloud shows every important element. In case of the navigation, objects only in the height of the AMR are critical. Generally, by increasing the resolution as on the right image, the edges become sharper and the image shows more details but with higher resolution comes more noise too.

Figure 4.4. Quality comparison of received depth images

4.2.3 Digital twin in simulation

Figure 4.5. Camera model and its transformation links in simulation

The introduced ROS RealSense wrapper also contains the 3D model of the D435i camera with the related launch files. This model is a detailed URDF file showed in Figure 4.5 The links between frames are also defined. This helps detection methods

to be able to handle recognised object to transform into the robot frame. For simulation, a camera plugin is also required to provide all the topics as they were in real world. This model file is ready to integrate with various robots into their URDF file.

4.3 Mobile robot

This robot is a custom-built AMR, based on an Intel NUC running Ubuntu 18.04.5 LTS. It has four separate Mecanum wheels to drive, 2 lidar sensor on the respecting sides of the robot base, and an Intel RealSense RGBD camera is mounted on front position. After minimal onboard calculation, the AMR forwards these data to its custom cloud controller from where it gets back velocity commands.

Figure 4.6. Real and simulated research AMR

The goal of this AMR is to present a solution for systems without running ROS on board and still be able to perform in a ROS-based architecture. I created two parts of the cloud control. An image processing node, which gets a depth image, then processes it in the cloud before integrating the resulting point cloud to the navigation stack. The second contribution is the adjustment of time synchronization between the device and the cloud time server. This includes creating a containerized Chrony time server and connecting it with the AMR local real time clock.

The most challenging part related to the AMR was the camera integration, where I used a similar RGBD camera as on the UR robot arm, with the sole difference that I could not rely on ROS packages in the physical device. The development environment also had some restrictions. Although the research NUC did not limited

to run Python 2.7, at receiver side whom I send the depth image data the cloud container runs ROS Melodic with Python 2.7 exclusively.

4.3.1 Network setup

The AMR has a built-in WiFi adapter in the NUC and it has also been extended with a 5G modem mounted on top of the AMRs to be able to connect to the server. There is a dedicated Docker image in the cloud where a custom AMR controller takes place with managing and controlling the related topics. The image processing is moved to a separate container which processes depth image then provides point cloud. The data is transmitted through WiFi connection for test purposes, and later it changes to cellular network to be prepared for operating over standalone 5G network.

4.3.2 Use case related image processing

I created a ROS package to extract point cloud data from depth image. In my case, the depth image does not contain colour information, so I only have to calculate the accurate distance of the pixels with the corresponding camera parameters. Below the code snippet shows how a depth image turned to point cloud based on triangulation. If a pixel value is not 0, the x, y, z coordinates can be calculated from the camera intrinsic parameters.

For point cloud extraction, the image matrix shall be traversed from pixel to pixel. Shadow projection could cause pixels without useful information. Therefore, these elements are defined to be zero, and will be left out from calculation. The depth value depends on the intensity of the actual pixel, and also influenced by individual camera parameters. The x and y coordinates are calculated from the location of the pixel on the original depth image, and intrinsic parameters are also taking into account during the calculation. The following code snippet show the transformation loop. The *camera_cx* and *camera_cy* parameters are the centre coordinates of the camera sensor. the *camera_factor* is a constant value calculated from the focal length given in metres and pixels.

Algorithm 1. C++ code for point cloud preparation:

```
1 for (int m = 0; m < depth_img.rows; m++)
2   for (int n = 0; n < depth_img.cols; n++)
3   {
4     ushort d = depth_img.ptr<ushort>(m)[n];
5
6     if (d == 0)
7       continue;
8
9     PointT p;
10
11     p.z = double(d) / camera_factor;
12     p.x = (n - camera_cx) * p.z / camera_fx;
13     p.y = (m - camera_cy) * p.z / camera_fy;
14
15     cloud -> points.push_back(p);
16   }
```

Although the point cloud visualization seems blurry on Figure 4.7 b) especially at greater distances, the important information contained by less than a metre. There is no need for point cloud data over the height of an AMR. This reduction helps reducing point cloud computational cost, and also allows AMRs to pass through gates and narrow corridors.

Figure 4.7. Colour image and raw point cloud visualization

4.3.3 Digital twin in simulation

In order to be able to provide simulations, the exact model has to be created in Gazebo environment. The components are either described in URDF or Xacro files to work with. Creating a custom AMR necessitate building a robot model from scratch. To help the process, with the spreading of ROS, robotic component manufacturers realized the potential of this community so they started to make robot model files that could be used for building up a robot from custom parts. The

robot model also includes four omnidirectional wheels, two SICK laserscanners, and a RealSense camera.

Figure 4.8. Mecanum wheel and lidar simulated models

These model files were ready to use, so after collecting the required components I could integrate them to a common robot model, and set up their exact location. Sensor location has an important role, because only an accurately placed model could provide useful measurements to be applied in real world. The simulated robot with its transformations presented on Figure 4.9.

Figure 4.9. Robot model and its transformation links in simulation

Simulation allows easy instantiating more robots into a common environment. To do so, robots should have unique name to be able to handled by. Instantiating more robots implies instantiating all the connected elements like the sensors but also the underlying transformation frames are need to be handled in separated namespaces. To achieve this, I extended the elements in the robot description file to be able to use namespace groups coherently with the components.

4.4 Robotic arm

The robotic arm has a similar cloud scheme as the AMR. It also follows distributed architecture where several elements are moved into the cloud or edge cloud. As Figure 4.10 shows, the connection between hardware elements and cloud control is provided by Raspberry Pi devices. All these devices reach the cloud environment through an 5G modem. To get rid of separate power supplies, every device is equipped with a power over ethernet (POE) hat.

Figure 4.10. UR3e robot with annotated equipment

The data forwarding nodes took place as the annotated devices presented on Figure 4.10. There is a camera controller node which is responsible for colour and depth image pre processing and forwarding. The robot control node is separated from the local Universal Robots control box, and runs on a Raspberry Pi. Because of this control node requires ultra-low latency network to operate, in test phases it could not take place in the cloud environment. The gripper control requires a control box to open and close the end-effector fingertips. All these components are connected to a router where from it can be forwarded through wireless or cellular

connection. Throughout the development phases it was used with WiFi, LTE and also 5G connection.

4.4.1 Network setup

All the components of the robotic system are prepared to connect and communicate over 5G. To achieve this, a Raspberry Pi serves as a gateway at the camera because of the lack of any direct connection. Although the UR3e compute box could be connected directly to the network, the interesting part would be to run from the cloud. Due to its ultra-low latency requirement, it is not yet possible to run from the cloud. Later, with the improvement of the experimental 5G network parameters, it could be also moved to the cloud. The 5G modem is also connected to the system through a Raspberry. It is a commercial SimCom 5G modem which connects the server with the mentioned devices. Figure 4.11 shows a schematic arrangement with the related components.

Figure 4.11. Physical elements of the robot

Although the publish-subscribe scheme publishes every frame, the image processing takes only one frame from the stream to work on. Taking this opportunity, it can be reduced to give a frame exactly when it is required to do so. Because of the camera has a warm-up time, it cannot be used directly. To achieve this, the idea is to combine PUB-SUB and REQ-REP communication schemes as Figure 4.12 presents.

Figure 4.12. Combined publish-subscribe and request-response networking patterns

According to this enhancement, the camera driver node running in the background always provides camera stream, but it will not transfer the whole stream over the network, it only provides stream for a local service server. This server provides only one image by grabbing a frame from the camera stream in case of an incoming request from the cloud. This frame is then processed in the cloud which serve as a basis of further robot movement calculations.

4.4.2 Use case related image processing

Image processing has to provide reliable real-time information to fulfill the demonstration task requirements. It combines techniques for handling both colour and depth information. The current problem could be separated into two phases: working with colour images and working with depth images. This task could have been accomplished by working only with the depth image, but for demonstration purposes, the colour image processing methods are also introduced here.

The task related to the colour image is to find a jenga-like black rectangular object on the table, if there are more, choose one considering whether the robot can reach it or not. It is based on a robust colour segmentation process in HSV colour space. The black colour of the jenga piece and its non-reflecting surface makes filtering for black colour possible and accurate, as Figure 4.13 shows. It also excludes objects when there is a measurable difference of the length of the sides, and its area. To prove its robustness, it has been successfully tested with strong light sources and different lighting conditions. With OpenCV, the orientation and exact position has

been extracted from the detection image. This is then sent to the robot to grip the object at the right place.

Figure 4.13. Before and after colour image processing

From the depth image, the goal is to extract the accurate distance and provide an illustrative image about the tower level measurement. Intel provides examples for depth images processing. Calculating the Z distance from the depth image is helped with a function, that returns the depth distance related to a 2D pixel coordinate.

Figure 4.14. Before and after depth image processing

Visualization was not as straightforward as it seems, because the gripper was too close to the camera thus distracting depth measurement. The idea was to equalize the histogram of the depth image, because a 1 cm difference in a 16 bit image cannot be distinguished by human eye. To help visualization, histogram equalization is applied to a region of interest only where jenga pieces could occur. In Figure 4.14 the distances of the tower corners are presented. Due to a shallow depth, histogram equalization results in displaying small differences with significantly changing colours. The distance is calculated as the median value of the intersecting jenga elements marked with the white dots.

In simulation, the implemented solution gives the following result. With simulated camera, both image stream includes less noise which gives here more accuracy and

sharper edges. The simulated images also contain the gripper tips, which are masked out not to disturb jenga detection. Depth detection also gives correct values from the noiseless images. On Figure 4.15 one can read out that the simulated jenga piece is exactly 2 cm high.

Figure 4.15. Image processing applied in simulated environment

4.4.3 Digital twin in simulation

The URDF model of the Universal Robots UR3e is available online from the UR repository. UR has an extensive and up to date codebase on GitHub to encourage open source development for real-world applications and also for Gazebo simulation.

Figure 4.16. Robot model and its transformation links in simulation

The bare robot model needs to be extended with the OnRobot end effector, with the camera and its 3D printed holder module and also with its physical surroundings. By joining the URDF files, just like at the AMR, a digital twin can be created. This gives a fully functioning simulated robot with the related ROS topics.

After properly integrating the elements together, on Figure 4.16 the corresponding transformations can be observed. These transformations play a key role in robot arm trajectory planning. When an RGBD camera is mounted onto the end effector, it could be connected to the robot TF-tree to provide transformation from the camera through the robot joints thus connecting with the world frame. This is a powerful help for pick and place jobs. When the 3D coordinates are available related to the RGBD camera, these coordinates could be transformed to the different frames of robot joints.

Chapter 5

Mobile robot validation use case

Nowadays AMRs are prepared to function as a collaborative taxi robot in modern factories and warehouses equipped with private cellular network. Mobile robots are aimed to operate over this network while all the smart control functions and processing elements located in the cloud, only the sensing and acting remain on the AMRs.

Figure 5.1. AMR simulated environment

There is also a digital twin representation from the environment, where these robots are being tested. Here the robots could demonstrate different navigation and planning capabilities before they released into the real world. In a simulation, robots cannot cause damage which is a cost-effective and safe way of development.

Both mobile robots are equipped with the ability of RGBD vision. This helps these robots not only to see colour images but to calculate distances from depth images and also to create a cloud map. This extension could provide a more secure application of AMRs extending planar laser scanners with 3D inspection.

5.1 Demonstration explained

For the purpose of research, development and testing, I created a simulated test track for the AMR. Here can be tested and validated the digital twin capabilities, finetune the navigation parameters and analyse its performance during operation. With accurate physics and models, simulation speeds up the development progress and makes remote work possible. This environment is shown in Figure 5.2. The following figures are aimed to show the simulation representation step by step and give an insight to the structures of the local and global costmap layers. The first image represents the simulated custom test area, including an AMR.

Figure 5.2. Simulated AMR test track

The blocking element on Figure 5.2 is just a virtual object in the simulation. This component ought to demonstrate the importance of spatial perception and object detection. Without the spatial information, AMRs would crash into objects that are either over or under the height of their laser scanners. I also removed the internal walls in the map to demonstrate the differences on the costmap layers. Now the map from the test track looks as follows:

Figure 5.3. Cloud provided global map

After the initial mapping procedure, there is an available global map provided by the map server node from the cloud. The AMR operates over this base layer, and

updates only a local segment with their sensory information. On Figure 5.3 the black lines indicate walls, the grey area is discovered while the remaining area is undiscovered. Here only the main walls are presented.

Figure 5.4. Global map with inflation layer

The inflation layer contains these colourful wall boundaries appearing on the global map. Its main function is to assign cost values to the occupied cells that decrease with distance. There are 5 symbols defined for costmap values as they relate to a robot. This layer helps different planner implementations to care or not about the robot footprint, giving enough information to handle situations [34].

Between the obstacle islands on Figure 5.5 there is a pink line without a black contour. This marks the objects that are left out during the initial mapping process and appeared afterwards. These elements are detected with either laser scanners or depth cameras. To inform other AMRs, this update is included by the global map to influence trajectory generation.

Figure 5.5. Local costmap over the inflation layer

On the bottom left corner of Figure 5.5 there is a green square indicating the AMR location with its footprint. AMCL implements the adaptive Monte Carlo localization using a particle filter to track the position of a robot against a known map. It takes a laser-based map, laser scan or point cloud topics and transform messages to match these input data to the map in order to detect if there is any drift occurring in the pose estimate based on the odometry.

Local costmap is a defined square area around the robot. As Figure 5.5 shows, rolling window keeps the robot in the centre of the local costmap as it moves throughout the world. It updates the local plan with the newly detected objects, correcting the global plan with unforeseeable elements. Walls that are not part of the global map are appears on the local costmap. The internal walls have cost here to influence local planner during the execution of the global plan.

Figure 5.6. Voxel layer over costmap layers

The top layer of this map is the voxel layer. The information comes from the depth cameras located on the front of the AMRs. The Spatio Temporal Voxel Layer [35] (STVL) plugin processes the point cloud as input data and provide spatial information to influence trajectory planning. On Figure 5.6 and on Figure 5.9 now the blocking elements turn visible through the voxel grid, and it is projected to the costmap layer to indicate the obstacles. This will prevent trajectory planning through that area.

5.2 Navigation extended with voxel layer

Voxel layer from point cloud and obstacle layer are responsible for marking obstacles on the costmap. The applied Spatio-Temporal Voxel Layer operates with voxels from point cloud data published by the depth image processing node. The same implementation works in real as well as simulated environments thus enabling modular digital twin development.

Without 3D cameras, objects can be recognised exclusively in the plane of laser scanners. Objects above and below could not be seen which easily could cause safety issues. As Figure 5.7 shows, the AMR stand in front of an obstacle clearly blocking its path. Although it could not cross, the element cannot be seen by the AMR exclusively with laser scanners as per the distant blue dots on Figure 5.8.

Figure 5.7. In-sight obstacle blocking the path

Figure 5.8. Object detection with lidar (blue) and 3D camera (yellow)

By utilizing a 3D front camera, detected objects will be projected to the 2D map as a new layer and will appear on the global costmap, helping the AMR in global trajectory planning. Clearly visible, that meanwhile the point cloud – marked with yellow dots – visualize the blocking element but because of its height, laser scanner rays go under the obstacle. Point cloud integration prevents the robot from colliding with elements over or under the height of the laser scanner. Figure 5.9 present objects that laser scanner could not detect. On the left, there is the silhouette of a table which turns out to be a not blocking element but, on the right a wall can

be observed where the AMR could not pass. The navigation is configured to take account of points that are less than a metre height. Because of the surface of the table is higher than that, only the table legs influence path planning thus the robot could go under the table.

Figure 5.9. Simulated AMR in front of obstacles

An important feature of the costmap layers is the temporality of objects. Voxels have expiration time thereby occupation over time can be configured. This layer is created to store time for each voxel after which the voxel will disappear from the map. This is an essential part of layer maintenance, because with permanent voxels the map would be unrecognisable due to dynamic objects. For example, multiple moving AMRs have to mark each other on the map strictly permanently, otherwise they would block the road, thus negatively affecting the trajectory generation.

5.3 General experiences

After applying the introduced depth image enhancement methods, the point cloud become much clearer but some dots are still caused noise. These are appeared less than 20 cm distance which is the minimal operating distance of the camera.

When I compared the depth image quality on all different resolution, I chose the middle way by setting 640x480. With this quality, the important details still appear on the image yet the size remain treatable.

In simulation, the realized system performed as expected. Because of the simulated camera plugin produces the depth image, the interesting part of the simulation was the point cloud preparation. To inspect the camera module related tasks, Figure 5.11 present the result of depth image processing based on Figure 5.10.

Figure 5.10. Depth image from simulated camera

Both images on Figure 5.11 were captured from rviz, showing the obstacles from point cloud. The yellow point cloud on the left image is generated by the gazebo plugin, meanwhile the white point cloud on the right image is generated by my depth image processing node. Due to the noiseless depth images, this could be considered as a validation of my method.

Figure 5.11. Point cloud comparison in simulation

Chapter 6

Robotic arm validation use case

The goal of this demonstration is to present the current capabilities of URLLC 5G network through a cloud robotic use case. It includes a complex robotic system with cooperative abilities. The network usage is presented by the image processing element, which forwards an image to extract information, then gets back a computed result. In this demonstration, the controller not yet placed into the cloud, but with further improved releases, standalone 5G will be able to handle such low latency required applications that now impossible to control from the cloud.

6.1 Demonstration explained

As an illustrative demonstration, the robot arm was programmed to build a jenga tower from small black wooden pieces. The robot detects the free wooden pieces by itself and place them to an exact location, following the build order. There is no pre-programmed initial jenga position or height, everything is measured and calculated on the fly. It is also prepared for cooperation, because before placement it measures first, where to put the next element.

For smart sensing, a depth camera is mounted on the robot arm, similar to the AMR setup. The tasks are involving visual servoing by the help of the introduced depth camera. To show its capabilities, colour and depth image processing steps are both involved in the demonstration.

From the aspect of network patterns, the idea is to combine the ROS publish-subscribe communication with request-response. Since the robot movement stops during the detection and measurement phase, it could be done by analysing only one colour and depth frame. This method significantly reduces the data transfer among the camera and cloud processing.

Figure 6.1. The realized system during live demonstration event

6.2 General experiences

During the live demonstration, multiple applications were connected to the same network which led to an increased latency. Taking the option of modularity, the robotic arm controller remained local, only the image processing was moved to the cloud. With the average size of the images changing between 200 KB and 300 KB sizes, the pilot network could handle the minimal load.

To be prepared for the changeable lighting conditions and reflections of the event, I created another node for monitoring the jenga detection. This node transmitted data through only the local network and does not use the 5G network. It was necessary for me to be able to adjust camera parameters to provide the correct thresholded image. I did the modifications with `rqt`, a ROS backend tool for interacting with robots during their runtime.

`Rqt` allows access to change camera parameters during operation such as brightness, contrast, exposure or saturation and more. To adapt the thresholding to the actual lighting conditions, this was a helpful tool to always provide the most accurate coordinates for gripping the object. The gripper also helped compensating in less accurate positions. Because of the gripper opens wide, the jenga does not necessarily have to be in an exact pose, during the closing process it will manage to be grasped.

Chapter 7

Measurements

The following section present the performance results of the network and cloud-based image processing. For latency measurements, I applied glass to glass method which is also called end-to-end latency because it measures the time it takes between the moment of action that happens in front of a camera (first glass), and the moment that a viewer sees this action on the screen (second glass). I used an online stopwatch to determine latency. The camera is faced to my notebook screen and forwards the encoded stream for cloud processing.

Figure 7.1. Latency measurement arrangement

I chose the introduced method because it measures latency end-to-end, including such elements like the camera readout time and so on. On the other hand, with this method a possible bottleneck is the 60 Hz refreshing rate of my screen. Because of the camera relies on the content of the screen, it could not be more accurate than $1/60$ s which could cause less accuracy in close values.

Besides latency, I also measured the benefits of utilizing my custom streaming method instead of going along with the image transport provided by ROS. I mea-

sure and compare the data traffic with different network and image parameters, then evaluate the advantages and limitations.

7.1 Data traffic measurement

An important quality of the realized system is the required bandwidth to operate with. First, I measured the ROS solution for image transport, then I compare it with my GStreamer solution and show the results. For traffic measurement purposes on ROS side, I used the internal topic bandwidth monitor, while for GStreamer traffic I used Interface TOP (IFTOP) which is a real time Linux network bandwidth tool. To measure exclusively the image transport, I filtered for the exact port where GStreamer is forwarding the stream. All the measurements reflect an average of 5 minute data traffic.

The performance of the publish-subscribe image streaming in ROS is summarized in Table 7.1. As expected, the raw image transport over ROS has the highest bandwidth requirement. All the measurements were done with 640x480 resolution and 30 FPS. These results are close to Intel’s official EtherSense realization, where for example the depth streaming with similar parameters took 13,88 MB/s.

Table 7.1. Measured transmission parameters with ROS.

<i>Source</i>	<i>Quality</i>	<i>Bandwidth</i>
raw colour image	raw bgr8	27,78 MB/s
raw depth image	raw mono16	13,81 MB/s
compressed colour image	100% JPEG	4,04 MB/s
compressed colour image	15% JPEG	0,21 MB/s
compressed depth image	100% JPEG	1,48 MB/s
compressed depth image	15% JPEG	0,26 MB/s

Although compressed image transport could significantly lower the transmitted data with giving up image quality, the hybrid method could present an even better solution. The idea of providing only one frame on request could minimize the data transfer. However, in the background the image streaming is still running, but image data remains in the edge, and does not go into the cloud unless it is requested.

The above-mentioned compression methods are also applied to the requested frame. This results in such a small size that could be transferred without difficulties. The size of only one colour frame with 15% JPEG quality is approximately 215.808 KB, the depth frame size with same parameters is 265.472 KB which meet the expectations.

Figure 7.2. Depth image streaming comparison

Comparing these results with the ROS streaming options, GStreamer could perform better up to more than an order of magnitude. Rather than compressing images one by one as ROS does, I used GStreamer with H.264 encoding where the inter frame compression significantly reduces the bandwidth consumption. It is important to note that static scenes coded with H.264 results in low data transmit, therefore my measurement contains still scenes and scenes in motion to collect realistic data. Because of comparing streams in different resolution, I set up GStreamer to forward with constant quality. To show a more revealing chart and visualize the differences, I applied logarithmic scaling.

Figure 7.3. Color image streaming comparison

Having examined the colour streaming, the parameters and measurement method remained unchanged. Here the results show similarities in the overhead of ROS transport against my implementation. Taking into account the image quality and the required bandwidth, the middle way is the most reasonable choice with 640x480 or 640x360 resolution in depth as well as colour streaming.

7.2 Latency measurement

My measurement arrangement is explained by Figure 7.1. There is a jenga element showed on my laptop screen to trigger the image processing. This is being watched by the camera connected to a Raspberry where the stream is forwarded to image processing to extract coordinates. From the actual processing device, only the coordinates and their sudden changes are presented. The pre-recorded video contains a jenga element which is suddenly moved to another position after exactly 5 *seconds*. These changes can be monitored alongside with a digital stopwatch to calculate the latency of the full process, glass-to-glass.

7.2.1 Measurement arrangement I.

With this method I measured with different arrangements to present the changes of latency values. The first simple measurement compares latency between wired and wireless connection. The arrangement showed on Figure 7.4, where the devices connected through a router. The wireless connection is marked with the blue dotted line while wired connection indicated with the black straight line. In all the following setups I measure the colour streaming in consistently 640x480 resolution with 30 FPS based on the previous data traffic measurements.

Figure 7.4. Arrangement I. network scheme

In this setup, the Raspberry forwards the colour image through a router over wired or wireless connection, and this connection ends in the laptop, where the image

processing receives the stream. It detects jenga from a pre recorded video and also shows a stopwatch that is also started alongside to be able to calculate end to end latency. This setup run for 10 minutes with screen recording, whereof I then calculate ten latency values separately. After collecting and evaluating the data, I summarized it in the following chart.

Figure 7.5. Arrangement I. latency results

At first sight, one can clearly differentiate between the compared image transport methods for the account of my GStreamer realization. ROS image transport cause 1,3506 *seconds* delay over wireless, and 1,2094 *s* over wired connection. As was to be expected, the wireless and wired measurements of the separate methods are stick together with a slight deflection in standard deviation. In this single hop architecture, wireless and wired connection does not show heavy differences. However, ROS latency shows significantly more deviation than GStreamer, which does not differ much. Meanwhile transmission with GStreamer generates 0,213 *s* for wired and 0,2174 *s* latency on average, ROS shows significantly higher values for latency characteristics. The higher variance caused by ROS is also visible from Figure 7.5 and the individual values are shown by Table 7.2.

Table 7.2. Latency characteristics for Arrangement I.

	ROS		GStreamer	
	wireless	wired	wireless	wireless
average	1,3501	1,2094	0,2128	0,2174
std dev	0,1045	0,0819	0,0277	0,0358

7.2.2 Measurement arrangement II.

Figure 7.6. Arrangement II. network scheme

Another arrangement is presented on Figure 7.6, where a server is included in the network. Therefore, I moved the image processing node into the server to function as it is intended to work like either the complete robot arm demonstration or the mobile robot scenario where the cloud server is similarly arranged. After inspecting Figure 7.6, the presented arrangement can be extended for cellular network measurements in the following way. The router could be changed for a switch and extending it with an 5G modem which connects to the server wirelessly. On receiver side, the laptop could be connected either through another 5G modem, or a compatible smartphone with tethering. The wireless connection options also showed by blue dotted line in Figure 7.6. The architecture does not change, but the latency values could show interesting results to compare.

Figure 7.7. Arrangement II. latency results

Turning back to the available devices as Figure 7.6, presents, the camera streams live information about the jenga and stopwatch through a router to the server. I

inspected these results from my laptop by connecting to the router by wire and wireless. After collecting data for 10 minutes, I picked the values from ten different moments and visualized the results of the two image transport method, both on wired and wireless connection. Figure 7.7 represents the collected data in a common chart. As I expected, there is a visible growth in the standard deviation of latency, where the most deviation is shown by the wireless ROS image transport. Now, there are significant difference between wired and wireless connection which shows the downside of applying ROS image transportation in wireless networks. To examine the exact differences, I arranged the average latency and the corresponding deviation at the different image transport methods in Table 7.3. As regards the bandwidth usage, the GStreamer realization here also shows favourable results. The average latency is 0,2223 *seconds* with cable connection, and 0,244 *s* on wireless transport.

Table 7.3. Latency characteristics for Arrangement II.

	ROS		GStreamer	
	wireless	wired	wireless	wired
average	1,3501	1,1237	0,244	0,2223
std dev	0,1045	0,1202	0,0662	0,0323

7.2.3 General experiences

During the measurement, GStreamer sometimes showed some corrupted frames between the I-frame intervals. The nature of this problem suggest that the error lies in the encoder parametrization. Because of H.264 based on inter-frame encoding, only the changes play vital role in sending a new frame. This could cause the following discrepancy.

Figure 7.8. Expected and received frame during measurement

Contrary to this unwanted effect, the measurement and application is still accurate, because the captured frame-to-frame differences are still appeared correctly

on time. In order to provide a solution, eliminating this effect is subject of further development.

7.3 Overall measurement evaluation

Of all the measurements taken, ROS image transport showed weaker performance. This could be due to the fact that ROS image transport normally operates with raw images, where the pixel values stored as separate string values. The inefficiency of this method is clearly presented here, in particular where wireless transport is utilized. However, in the frames sent over either wired or wireless connection, no frame corruption was detected.

On the other hand, my realization with GStreamer performed even better than I expected. According to the measurements, it really could serve as an alternate image transport method in real applications. With such low end-to-end latency, where no significant deviation appeared, it could be utilized in various visual aided robotic scenarios.

Chapter 8

Conclusion

Combining robotics with cellular networks brought a new era into industrial robotic research and development. New challenges have to be tackled with a focus on providing proper communication and data traffic setup. Sensor data processing as well as the control software is decoupled from the local robot hardware and placed into the cloud.

In field of cloud robotics, there are trade-offs that have to be handled in the right way. With the steady appreciation of robotic safety features, more and more sensors are being integrated but it comes with a cost. This data has to be sent through a limited bandwidth and keep as low latency as possible in order to give robots the new instruction on time. In this thesis I offered an alternative solution for real time video streaming. Cellular networks are not ready for this amount of real time data yet but the appearance of 5G will pave the way for handling the increased needs.

From the architecture design through the realization my goal was to form the components as robust and modular as possible. Cameras are versatile devices that could be helpful in various robotic projects that require increased accuracy and safety. Mounting the device rigidly onto the end effector gives more opportunity with being a movable camera than a still one. This eye in hand incorporation could get a better overview of a workspace.

Implementing a robotic system that relies on visual information is a challenging task. It requires to see the system as a whole picture as it contains many elements. In my task, the most challenging part was to solve the low latency video streaming because this is the key element in both robotic applications. The camera element is designed to be such modular element that could be used in several robotic projects and provide easy integration from both software and hardware aspect.

In my project the modularity also plays a vital role. It is interesting to see, how elements – either software or hardware – could be combined and reused in different applications with other components. I chose a depth camera to present this versatility for a mobile robot, a robotic arm alongside with their simulated digital twin model. With the spreading of remote working opportunities, sometimes there are limited options to work on physical devices. To prepare for these cases I created a simulation environment and a digital twin model of a mobile robot. Due to the accurate physical engines, the development of the physical device could be built upon the results provided by simulation.

After the realization and testing, the network measurements are confirmed the right choice of hardware and software components. I created a measurement arrangement where the network parameters could be measured, independently of the connection type. It shows comparable results with the now available wired and wireless technologies. According to the evaluation, I successfully presented an alternative image transport method with a more favourable transmission parameter. As a general solution, it is ready to be integrated into various robotic application and there is also an opportunity for further development.

8.1 Future work

Contrary to certain expectations that human workers will be displaced by robots, the real trend is to utilize collaborative robots besides humans to work with. This change necessitates robots to be aware about their full surroundings real time that seems to be the real challenge. Providing reliable safety features requires more sensory information to process. In case of cloud robotics, this appears in a significant increase of network usage.

As I inspected, common industrial robots are not fully equipped with spatial sensors yet, but with the appearance of collaborative robotic arms, it is about to change. Robotic appliances and applications become more user friendly, and many leaves the exclusive world of assembly lines in order to cope and help with more versatile and general tasks.

In order to cope with the data expansion, networks have to provide wide bandwidth and stable ultra-low latency communication options. The improvement of these resources could lead the way on improving cloud robotics to be able to handle huge amount of data produced by various sensors robots equipped with.

Chapter 9

Summary

In this project, I integrated spatial sensing capabilities to an industrial autonomous mobile robot and to an industrial robot arm. Throughout a specified demonstration task, I presented the improved capabilities of the devices. All the robots are following the design patterns of cloud robotics over 5th generation mobile network: The sensory data processing is taken from onboard computers and placed to cloud computing devices, only the acting commands are being sent back to the device.

When I designed the common parts, my ambition was to provide a general solution for camera integration which can be attached to several industrial robots and use it also in simulation. I showed a use case for integrating spatial detection into mobile robot navigation, and another one for accurate measurements based on depth images.

I worked with colour as well as depth images, where the latter serves as a basis of point cloud processing. Due to its increasing usage, more and more industrial robotic object detection tasks base on point cloud information. My goal is to follow the cloud robotic architecture and place computational jobs into the cloud and only the necessary pre-processing tasks remain on board.

I showed, how the ROS image transportation could be replaced by a custom solution that significantly reduces data traffic. It is designed to be a general component that could be adapted in different robotic scenarios like object detection tasks. During my work I got a deep insight into point cloud generation, processing and transferring it over 5G network. As a result, robots now able to take into account their surroundings and use spatial sensing integrated into their movement. The camera is designed to be such modular element that can be shared between robots. In case of remote work, robots are also available from simulation to work with.

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